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A STATISTICAL PERSPECTIVE ON CAPILLARY ABSORPTION RATE AS CALCULATED ACCORDING TO THE IRAM 1871 METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The capillary absorption rate is used as a parameter indicative of the transport properties of concrete. The method is standardized by IRAM 1871. According to this procedure, the capillary absorption rate is calculated by a linear regression using the set of weight increments by capillary absorption of water over time of all samples belonging to the same group. That is, this linear regression is not calculated individually per sample, but is done for the whole series. In addition, a specific criterion is applied for the elimination of outliers. Usually, a set of experimental results can be approximated by a normal distribution. However, in the case of capillary absorption rate, the calculation methodology according to IRAM 1871 causes uncertainties from the statistical point of view. This paper presents a statistical analysis of experimental data from 55 samples of the same concrete, and of virtual data constructed from the experimental dispersion obtained. Inferences are made on the probabilities of occurrence of results, and it is found that, although the weight increments recorded in the test show normality according to their experimental character, this cannot be directly transposed to the value of the capillary absorption rate calculated from them.

INTRODUCTION

The capillary absorption test allows a quantitative evaluation of the moisture transport properties of concrete. The capillary absorption rate (S) is not properly applicable to the performance design for durability of structures, but it is a reliable index of the performance of a reinforced concrete structure in aggressive environments. Studies that verify correlations between S and other transport parameters are still pending (1). CIRSOC 201:2005 (2) incorporates the prescriptive limit of $4 \text{ g}/(\text{m}^2/\text{s}^{1/2})$ for the S of concrete to be used in structures in aggressive environments. This prescriptive limitation of S in the design of structures raises some questions related to the obtaining of the parameter, due to the specific methodology by which it is calculated.

IRAM 1871 (3) establishes that S is calculated from a linear regression on the set of mass increment densities (C_{it}) of at least three specimens, as a function of the square root of time. The data set excludes extreme values that deviate by more than 15% from the mean of the mass increment densities for each test time (C_t), as well as those C_{it} that are not between 10 and 90% of the capillary absorption capacity of the concrete (C). These limitations imply that in the calculation of S not always all the experimental data are used and a centralization of the results may tend to occur.

The centralization of S results would be caused mainly by the joint regression and the elimination of those C_{it} outside the $0.85-1.15 C_t$ limits. From the statistical point of view, the elimination of extreme results obtained reduces the domain of results in a dynamic way from the mean value of the set of samples. In this, there is the added question that the minimum number of samples is only three, but increasing it de facto modifies the effective elimination of values. At the same time, since the limits for data elimination depend on the mean value of the set, increasing the number of samples means a lower incidence of each value. In any case, the test procedure reduces the probability of extreme values to zero. It is then important to consider how in the case of S , which arises from a selected set of points rather than the total number of points, at least one specific causal for the statistical distribution of its results can be found.

Therefore, the distribution of S will show differences from that of C_{it} . The increment recorded will be the increment actually revealed by the specimen when weighed. This assumes a distribution resulting from mere experimentation, which corresponds to the possibility of errors in sampling, compaction, preparation, weighing, or location of the sample, among others, and which are all parameters in principle intrinsically random, and therefore, with a naturally normal distribution. This statistical description of C_{it} does not associate its variation with any particular variable but is the result of the sum of possibilities.

On the other hand, the elimination of extreme data can affect the calculation of S in the sense of linearizing the parameter with the square root of time. It is known that this is a simplification and that the shape of the curve is related to a power of time, which is close to 0.25 (4) instead of the value of 0.5 adopted in IRAM 1871. This implies that if there is a tendency or a greater probability of elimination of data in the zones of initial or final periods of the test, this would imply a favorable moment for a positive or negative turn of the straight line obtained by regression, since the experimental curve of capillary absorption will be located below the regression straight line in these zones. Likewise, this same simplification causes that the extension of the duration of the test implies a decay of the line obtained by regression, since the data incorporated with longer test times imply a greater number of points with negative residuals with respect to the capillary absorption line as a function of the square root of time.

This paper analyzes the statistical implications of the results of four aspects of the capillary absorption rate calculation: the simplified linearization with respect to the square root of time, the elimination of extreme values, the dynamic determination of the test duration, and the single regression to the set of data obtained from all the specimens belonging to a series. The analysis is performed on the basis of experimental results of 55 specimens obtained from a total of 5 batches of a conventional concrete mix. From this set of results, a statistical model is built to analyze probabilistically the occurrence of values and their implications with respect to the analysis that merit experimental values obtained for S by means of the methodology contemplated in IRAM 1871.

METODOLOGY

A proportioning of conventional concrete (Table 1) was computed, and five batches of the same mix were made, using various water-reducing admixtures. Eleven 10 cm x 20 cm

cylindrical specimens were molded for each batch and cured in a humid chamber for 28 days. Then, 5 cm thick samples were sawn to form the specimens, as required for the capillary absorption test according to IRAM 1871, which were waterproofed on their lateral cylindrical face. The number of values obtained for each S_{xx} is the result of the possible combinations of specimens within the group of 11 taken from by xx.

Table 1: Concrete proportioning.

Materials	kg/m ³
Water	153
OPC 40	345
Fine siliceous sand	183
Coarse siliceous sant	724
Crushed granite 6-20	1000
High-range water reducer (l/m ³)	1.75-1.90
Air (%)	4.5-5.5

RESULTS AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Table 2 presents the mass increment densities as a function of the square root of time for all specimens analyzed. The C_{it} values were found to conform to the normal distribution. Using Kolmogorov-Smirnov (with Lilliefors significance correction) and Shapiro-Wilk tests, the normality of the totality of the C_{it} data sets, grouped in 11 specimens from each of the 5 batches, was verified for each test time (t). This is consistent with the experimental nature of the C_{it} values, as indicated above. Thus, it is assumed that the experimental data C_{it} presents a random distribution, and that the modifications that arise in the statistics of S are the result of the computation procedure for this parameter from the set of samples. Indeed, the distribution of S_{01} conforms to a normal distribution, tested by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (with Lilliefors significance correction) and Shapiro-Wilk tests.

It was then verified whether the groups of values obtained for the five batches can be analyzed as a whole, as representative of a single population corresponding to the dosage studied. A check for the existence of significant differences was performed by multifactorial analysis of variance between the groups of C_{it} values, which are those originating from S and which do not present specific non-random limitation. First, the homogeneity of the variances of the C_{it} values was tested by means of Levene's test with the F statistic, applied for each batch and t separately, and the null hypothesis could not be rejected for any of the test times. This same homoscedasticity is only verified if time is considered as the grouping variable, which is influenced by the different rate of weight increase of each cake. It is therefore important to keep in mind that normality and homoscedasticity between groups is only verified for each particular time and the analysis of variance cannot be performed without grouping by test times.

Table 2. Mass increment densities as a function of the square root of time.

t (hours)	0.5	1	2	3	4	5	6	24	48	72	96	120	144	168	
AH	1	402.34	502.93	644.26	711.74	763.94	799.59	837.79	1121.72	1298.70	1420.94	1524.07	1604.28	1674.31	1734.15
	2	386.05	482.56	613.70	674.82	729.57	765.22	795.77	1078.43	1255.41	1378.92	1476.96	1559.72	1632.29	1697.23
	3	419.66	524.57	650.63	707.92	753.76	781.77	809.78	1059.34	1231.22	1356.00	1457.86	1543.17	1613.19	1675.58
	4	370.77	463.46	586.96	645.53	691.37	728.29	755.03	1013.50	1180.29	1293.61	1382.74	1452.77	1520.25	1577.54
	5	409.47	511.84	631.53	691.37	735.93	770.31	799.59	1061.88	1236.32	1352.18	1451.49	1534.25	1605.56	1667.94
	6	415.59	519.48	673.54	748.66	807.23	847.98	888.72	1207.03	1413.30	1557.17	1681.95	1786.36	1878.03	1954.42
	7	393.18	491.47	628.98	701.55	752.48	793.23	827.61	1126.82	1326.72	1483.32	1608.10	1713.78	1811.82	1888.21
	8	467.53	584.42	758.85	845.43	906.55	949.84	988.03	1324.17	1553.35	1713.78	1843.65	1960.79	2061.37	2149.23
	9	419.66	524.57	669.72	742.30	793.23	835.25	867.08	1168.83	1362.37	1494.78	1599.19	1687.04	1757.07	1818.19
	10	440.03	550.04	696.46	767.76	818.69	860.71	892.54	1191.75	1384.01	1520.25	1629.75	1721.42	1806.73	1875.48
	11	387.06	483.83	614.97	682.46	735.93	774.13	807.23	1100.08	1283.43	1410.75	1512.61	1595.37	1674.31	1739.25
AR	1	368.73	460.91	571.68	645.53	701.55	744.85	780.50	1082.25	1280.88	1427.30	1544.44	1647.57	1729.06	1797.81
	2	411.51	514.39	658.26	735.93	791.95	831.43	870.90	1185.39	1391.65	1549.53	1684.50	1791.45	1875.48	1951.88
	3	384.01	480.01	639.17	723.20	793.23	836.52	877.26	1240.14	1462.95	1614.47	1740.52	1844.92	1936.60	2005.35
	4	363.64	454.55	578.05	639.17	692.64	729.57	763.94	1038.96	1219.76	1340.72	1443.85	1530.43	1605.56	1661.58
	5	399.29	499.11	635.35	709.19	760.12	802.14	836.52	1130.64	1319.08	1440.03	1539.35	1624.65	1697.23	1759.62
	6	372.80	466.01	593.33	663.36	716.83	756.30	790.68	1077.16	1264.33	1395.47	1506.24	1600.46	1675.58	1741.79
	7	311.69	389.61	518.21	581.87	637.89	674.82	707.92	993.13	1166.29	1282.15	1380.19	1459.13	1529.16	1587.73
	8	398.27	497.84	623.89	695.19	751.21	789.41	822.51	1091.17	1256.69	1366.19	1456.59	1535.53	1604.28	1660.30
	9	341.23	426.54	546.22	613.70	662.08	697.74	733.39	976.57	1135.73	1237.59	1322.90	1392.92	1454.04	1503.70
	10	354.47	443.09	558.95	618.79	667.18	697.74	728.29	970.21	1128.09	1229.95	1319.08	1389.10	1450.22	1506.24
	11	394.19	492.74	625.16	690.10	737.21	774.13	803.41	1070.79	1238.86	1349.63	1438.76	1520.25	1583.91	1638.66
AS	1	353.96	453.27	562.77	623.89	668.45	702.83	729.57	979.12	1163.74	1277.06	1368.73	1452.77	-	-
	2	362.87	462.19	576.78	645.53	696.46	733.39	760.12	1021.14	1221.04	1336.90	1435.83	1518.97	-	-
	3	378.15	478.74	586.96	654.45	700.28	734.66	762.67	1026.23	1219.76	1334.36	1427.30	1512.61	-	-
	4	422.72	527.12	642.99	718.11	772.86	808.51	839.06	1117.90	1315.26	1434.94	1534.25	1620.83	-	-
	5	355.23	455.82	571.68	640.44	695.19	724.47	760.12	1018.59	1175.20	1326.72	1429.85	1515.16	-	-
	6	387.06	508.02	631.53	704.10	762.67	797.05	833.97	1121.72	1338.17	1469.32	1583.91	1683.22	-	-
	7	370.51	467.28	575.50	639.17	691.37	727.02	755.03	1031.32	1232.50	1362.37	1466.77	1563.54	-	-
	8	421.44	536.03	664.63	737.21	793.23	830.15	860.71	1161.19	1385.28	1524.07	1637.39	1737.97	-	-
	9	407.44	510.57	621.34	686.28	735.93	770.31	799.59	1063.16	1278.33	1406.93	1513.88	1605.56	-	-
	10	378.15	483.83	602.24	664.63	730.84	769.04	800.87	1084.80	1306.34	1437.49	1557.17	1666.67	-	-
	11	357.78	457.09	565.32	628.98	681.18	714.29	746.12	1010.95	1207.03	1333.08	1452.77	1545.71	-	-
AD	1	409.98	500.38	614.97	679.91	728.29	767.76	799.59	1080.98	1308.89	1450.22	1568.63	1673.04	-	-
	2	404.89	499.11	604.79	665.90	719.38	747.39	774.13	1037.69	1241.41	1363.64	1473.14	1568.63	-	-
	3	444.36	543.67	656.99	724.47	771.58	805.96	840.34	1124.27	1305.07	1437.49	1557.17	1647.57	-	-
	4	371.79	454.55	560.23	616.25	664.63	696.46	728.29	976.57	1158.65	1273.24	1368.73	1454.04	-	-
	5	399.80	495.29	607.34	674.82	724.47	757.58	788.14	1056.79	1250.32	1361.09	1460.41	1546.99	-	-
	6	364.15	450.73	542.40	598.42	640.44	672.27	699.01	925.65	1117.90	1222.31	1310.16	1382.74	-	-
	7	380.70	466.01	569.14	631.53	678.64	709.19	739.75	974.03	1108.99	1214.67	1302.52	1375.10	-	-
	8	415.08	516.94	630.25	697.74	748.66	781.77	811.05	1059.34	1209.58	1324.17	1428.57	1507.52	-	-
	9	366.69	446.91	537.31	585.69	628.98	659.54	683.73	907.82	1045.33	1157.37	1246.50	1326.72	-	-
	10	379.43	467.28	558.95	614.97	665.90	690.10	716.83	944.74	1075.89	1181.57	1263.05	1333.08	-	-
	11	402.34	486.38	579.32	646.81	686.28	714.29	744.85	991.85	1138.28	1246.50	1338.17	1420.94	-	-
AV	1	424.75	530.94	664.63	732.11	786.86	831.43	873.44	1200.66	1412.02	1564.81	1690.86	1797.81	1890.76	1964.61
	2	403.36	504.20	640.44	709.19	760.12	808.51	840.34	1151.01	1349.63	1493.51	1614.47	1716.33	1813.09	1883.12
	3	431.88	539.85	682.46	755.03	807.23	853.07	892.54	1214.67	1429.85	1587.73	1722.69	1842.38	1942.96	2019.36
	4	459.38	574.23	701.55	767.76	811.05	861.98	892.54	1212.12	1415.84	1592.82	1687.04	1793.99	1884.39	1960.79
	5	456.33	570.41	715.56	784.32	836.52	886.17	918.01	1241.41	1451.49	1596.64	1716.33	1819.46	1908.59	1979.89
	6	452.25	565.32	686.28	743.57	790.68	826.33	861.98	1133.18	1306.34	1437.49	1540.62	1624.65	1704.87	1764.71
	7	424.75	530.94	667.18	734.66	784.32	823.79	849.25	1140.82	1322.90	1451.49	1560.99	1651.39	1735.43	1804.18
	8	433.92	542.40	672.27	733.39	785.59	821.24	855.62	1147.19	1343.27	1485.87	1604.28	1703.59	1791.45	1869.12
	9	452.25	565.32	710.47	784.32	842.88	892.54	934.56	1302.52	1545.71	1734.15	1886.94	2020.63	2119.94	2203.98
	10	452.25	565.32	700.28	770.31	828.88	873.44	909.09	1232.50	1456.59	1623.38	1760.89	1888.21	1984.98	2067.74
	11	464.48	580.60	721.93	793.23	850.52	898.91	939.65	1297.43	1544.44	1743.06	1909.86	2069.01	2178.51	2281.65

The analysis of variance of the C_{it} groups divided by batch and t-test showed significant differences in all tests (with F-statistic values greater than 8.59). Subsequent Scheffé and Bonferroni tests yielded equal groupings. In general, the Scheffé test is considered more conservative but also more used than the Bonferroni test; it was decided to consider both for the contrast since the latter is imposed in several areas (5). Table 3 shows the groupings according to the differentiability of means at the 95% confidence level for the different t-tests. It can be seen that AV consistently differs from the rest of the batches, and only in some test times can it be associated with AH. The other three series present low discordance, and at the other extreme, the AD series can only at its beginning and end of capillary absorption be associated with AH.

The means (μ) and standard deviations (σ) of C_t for each batch are presented in Table 4. The range of differences between the pastes should be highlighted, where AV (batch with the maximum capillarity) presents equivalent means from 12% to 23% higher than the means for AD (batch with the minimum capillarity) as t increases.

Unlike S_{01} , the normality for S_{03} to S_{10} is limited due to the centralization of results caused by the elimination of extreme points and joint regression. The S_{xx} data are not strictly independent of each other, since each C_{it} partially gives rise to a certain number of S_{xx} values. For example, when S_{03} , S_{05} , and S_{08} are analyzed for each batch, each specimen is involved in the calculation of 45, 210, and 120 of the total 165, 462, and 165 values in each group, respectively. Still, the incidence of each specimen decreases as S_{xx} increases. Descriptive statistics for S_{xx} are presented in Table 5. From the Pearson's skewness coefficients, a tendency to right-skewed distributions (mean greater than the median) is noted. Likewise, the elimination of extreme data and the single regression calculation system, which tends to polarize the values towards the most frequent behavior of the set, should favor the kurtosis coefficient and the centralization of values. This tendency is relative and cannot be completely confirmed.

Table 3. Definition of homogeneous subsets, with 95% confidence according to Scheffé.

t (hours)	0.5	1	2	3	4	5	6	24	48	72	96	120	144	168
AD	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	-	-
AS	A	A	A-B	A	A	-	-							
AR	A	A	A-B	A	A	A	A							
AH	A-B	A-B	B-C	A-B	A-B	A	A							
AV	B	B	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	B	B	B	B

Table 4: Statistics of weight gain densities.

series	AH		AR		AS		AD		AV	
	μ	σ								
0.5	410.88	27.32	376.94	31.23	387.99	29.69	396.81	27.43	443.81	17.85
1	513.60	34.15	471.17	39.04	493.81	35.04	487.17	34.06	554.77	22.31
2	652.95	46.78	602.12	48.66	610.48	41.04	590.91	42.44	691.29	23.50
3	721.23	53.93	672.75	54.74	679.02	45.48	652.61	48.02	759.37	25.03
4	773.06	57.26	727.56	58.21	733.13	47.97	700.23	50.43	812.09	26.94
5	811.09	59.94	766.44	60.89	768.58	49.54	731.77	52.32	857.09	29.14
6	844.13	62.85	801.46	63.34	799.62	50.38	761.34	54.40	892.67	30.63
24	1134.1	85.52	1090.46	95.04	1075.89	65.71	1013.21	76.07	1213.08	53.98
48	1322.75	102.86	1275.20	115.87	1279.95	82.08	1185.27	98.92	1423.63	74.69
72	1455.38	115.97	1401.21	135.18	1409.34	85.14	1301.61	109.67	1581.91	94.61
96	1563.44	127.45	1506.49	151.54	1516.94	90.42	1400.86	122.94	1708.36	111.91
120	1653.65	140.10	1594.85	164.99	1610.72	96.11	1484.95	132.61	1820.92	132.01
144	1733.41	150.58	1668.90	175.00	-	-	-	-	1914.81	138.74
168	1801.01	159.00	1730.90	183.04	-	-	-	-	1991.95	148.59

Table 5: Statistics of capillary absorption rates as a function of the number of specimens.

		S ₀₃	S ₀₄	S ₀₅	S ₀₆	S ₀₇	S ₀₈	S ₀₉
AH	μ	2.25	2.23	2.24	2.23	2.24	2.23	2.23
	Median	2.24	2.22	2.23	2.22	2.23	2.23	2.23
	Asim. Pearson	0.35	0.32	0.46	0.51	0.41	0.28	0.43
	Curtosis	1.21	0.85	-0.29	1.57	0.30	1.16	1.11
	Q1	2.19	2.17	2.18	2.19	2.20	2.20	2.21
	Q3	2.31	2.28	2.29	2.27	2.26	2.25	2.25
AR	μ	2.22	2.20	2.20	2.20	2.19	2.18	2.18
	Median	2.20	2.19	2.19	2.18	2.18	2.17	2.17
	Asim. Pearson	0.49	0.38	0.51	0.57	0.54	0.53	0.44
	Curtosis	0.58	1.03	0.38	-0.82	-0.90	-0.97	-0.97
	Q1	2.13	2.14	2.14	2.14	2.14	2.14	2.14
	Q3	2.29	2.27	2.27	2.25	2.24	2.23	2.22
AS	μ	2.18	2.17	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18
	Median	2.18	2.17	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18
	Asim. Pearson	0.12	-0.07	-0.02	0.02	-0.10	0.01	-0.13
	Curtosis	3.10	2.08	-0.38	-0.38	-0.40	-0.44	-0.53
	Q1	2.13	2.14	2.15	2.15	2.16	2.16	2.16
	Q3	2.22	2.21	2.21	2.20	2.20	2.19	2.19
AD	μ	2.08	2.04	2.00	1.98	1.98	1.98	1.97
	Median	2.05	2.00	1.98	1.97	1.97	1.97	1.96
	Asim. Pearson	0.69	0.81	0.67	0.54	0.45	0.50	0.32
	Curtosis	-0.90	-0.19	1.45	4.72	9.33	10.65	29.94
	Q1	1.98	1.95	1.94	1.94	1.93	1.94	1.94
	Q3	2.20	2.09	2.03	2.01	2.00	1.99	1.98
AV	μ	2.30	2.28	2.28	2.27	2.27	2.26	2.26
	Median	2.30	2.29	2.28	2.27	2.26	2.26	2.26
	Asim. Pearson	0.11	-0.06	0.03	0.10	0.19	0.09	0.04
	Curtosis	-0.37	-0.43	-0.58	-0.53	-0.27	-0.38	-0.46
	Q1	2.25	2.23	2.23	2.23	2.23	2.23	2.24
	Q3	2.36	2.34	2.33	2.31	2.30	2.29	2.28

Next, it is of interest to verify the incidence of the elimination of data that do not satisfy $0.85C_t < C_{it} < 1.15C_t$. Figure 1 shows the evolution with t of the coefficient of variation (CV). With the exception of AS, the relative dispersion increases progressively with t . This implies an increase with t of the probability of data elimination under the constraint $0.85C_t < C_{it} < 1.15C_t$. Assuming concrete as a composite material, it would be expected that the initial measurements, involving a smaller volume of tested material (as a function of the advance in depth of the capillary absorption front), would show greater scatter than subsequent ones. On the contrary, these experimental results show a variability in the intrinsic capillarity of the specimens, which differ to a greater degree as the volume of material tested is larger and more representative of each specimen. Considering this and the greater relative error in the weighing for the initial determinations due to its degree of precision, Figure 2 presents the values of coefficients of variation to which the average variation in the determinations up to and including 6 h of testing has been discounted. Thus, the incremental trend of the dispersion can be seen more clearly from the measurements after 24 h of testing.

A singularity to be taken into account with respect to t of this non-uniform distribution of data removed is the shape of the capillary absorption curve and its relation to the straight line with which it is approximated by linear regression with the square root of t .

The resulting values of S_{05} are then analyzed. The number of 5 specimens was selected as it implies a sufficient representativeness of the batch, while providing a large number of combinations to allow a reliable statistical analysis and being practical from the number of view of experimental recreation. The variances of S_{05} for the five batches are not homogeneous (verified by Levene's test with the F statistic). From this, significant differences were determined between the means of S_{05} for each batch (Dunnett's C-test was applied, for pairwise comparison of batches, based on the Student's range and suitable when the

variances are unequal and the number of values is sufficiently large, in this case, 462 per batch). Most relevant is the occurrence of batches showing significant differences according to C_{it} but not according to S_{05} .

Figure 3 shows the contrast between the dispersion of results of the two batches with the most extreme values (AV and AD). The curves corresponding to the 5 and 95% percentiles are presented as a form of non-parametric contrast for C_{it} and for S_{05} . It can be seen that the S_{05} distributions for AV and AD tend to be closer to the distributions for C_{it} from which they were calculated. Even so, the analysis of variance confirms that the groups are significantly differentiable whether C_{it} or S_{05} is considered. In addition, a modification in the variation between C_{it} and S_{05} can be noted. While AV and AD present similar dispersions for C_{it} , the dispersion of S_{05} for AV is greatly diminished with respect to AD. This is a result of the fact that the calculation for AV is including two more weighing periods than for AD, and this homogenizes its regression results for S_{05} due to the simultaneous imposition of this sustained test duration on a conventional relative value and the determination of S_{05} from the square root of time. This is clearly seen when comparing the AR and AD series (Figure 4), where the former presents greater absolute dispersion than the latter in the case of C_{it} but the relationship is reversed for S_{05} . This homogenization occurs for all the pastes, as can be seen in Figure 5. This implies that adopting one more or one less period for the calculation of S may imply a greater or lesser homogenization of the probable results, respectively. On the other hand, the duration of the test has no incidence on the dispersion of weight increment densities between different specimens. Therefore, the calculation procedure could be inducing an apparent homogenization for the interpretation of results. In Figure 5 it can be seen that the dispersion decreases between C_{it} and S_{05} for all cases except one (corresponding to the 95% percentile for AD). This leads to think that the calculation procedure is not compatible with the linearization of the capillary absorption rate with respect to the square root of time, and the conventional relative limit for the duration of the test. It is important to analyze the possibility of modifying one or two of these three criteria.

Figure 1. Evolution of CV with t.

Figure 2. CV minus average CV between 0.5 and 6 h, with respect to t.

Figure 3: Perc. 5 and 95% for C_{it} y S_{05} , AV y AD.

Figure 4: Perc. 5 and 95% for C_{it} y S_{05} , AR y AD.

Figure 5: Percentiles 5 and 95% for S_{05} and C_{it} with respect to their respective average values. [Translation of axes titles: y-axes: Percentiles 5 and 95% for S_{05} with respect to the median of S_{05} (%); x-axis: Average values for percentiles 5 and 95% with respect to average C_{it} (%)]

CONCLUSIONS

The C_{it} values conform to the normal distribution, however, the normality of the distributions for S_{xx} is limited due to the centralization of results by the elimination of extreme points and by the joint regression to the data set considered.

The statistical analysis of the results presented allowed us to determine a directionality of the results coming from the method of calculating the capillary absorption rate. In this regard, there are two fundamental points to be taken into account. First, the calculation method reduces the dispersion of results with respect to the densities of weight increase. Although this does not necessarily have significant implications on the value obtained for the capillary absorption rate, it is important to note that it masks the variability of results inherent to the test and to concrete as a composite and heterogeneous material. Based on this, it is necessary to note the need to establish a range for the reliability of the value obtained.

In addition, the criterion adopted for the elimination of extreme points in IRAM 1871 means a higher probability of discarding values for longer test times, which implies a propensity to obtain lower capillary absorption coefficients due to this criterion.

The variable duration of the test (determined dynamically according to weight gain), the least squares regression to the set of values of all specimens as a whole, the elimination of data that do not meet the criterion $0.85C_{it} < C_{it} < 1.15C_{it}$, and the forced linearization with respect to the square root of time, are criteria that, applied simultaneously, establish conditions for the calculation to imply a directionality that systematically differentiates the results obtained by the calculation with respect to the results obtained by experimentation.

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